

CLINICAL INTERVENTION AND OUTCOMES IN HIGH-RISK PATIENTS WITH UPPER GASTROINTESTINAL BLEEDING

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Abstract

OBJECTIVE: To determine the frequency of clinical interventions and outcomes in high-risk patients presenting with upper gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding.

METHODOLOGY: This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted at the Department of Medicine, Indus Medical College Hospital over six months. A total of 119 patients aged 30–70 years of either gender with a history of upper GI bleeding (black/tarry stools for three days or hematemesis for ≥ 1 hour) were included. Data regarding demographics, comorbidities, and laboratory parameters were recorded. Clinical interventions (blood transfusion, endoscopy) and outcomes (discharged, referred, death) were assessed. Mean \pm standard deviation (SD) was calculated for quantitative variables, while median (IQR) was used for non-normal data after Shapiro-Wilk testing. Post-stratification chi-square/Fisher's exact test was applied, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

RESULTS: The mean age was 52.4 ± 10.6 years, with 61.3% males. Anemia (56.3%), raised ESR (53.8%), raised C-reactive protein (50.4%), and *Helicobacter pylori* infection (52.1%) were the most frequent findings. Blood transfusion was required in 59.7% and endoscopy was performed in 69.7% of patients. Most patients were discharged (72.3%), while 17.6% were referred and 10.1% died. Hypoalbuminemia, anemia, and hepatitis C infection were significantly associated with poor outcomes ($p \leq 0.05$).

CONCLUSION: Upper GI bleeding in high-risk patients is associated with significant morbidity and mortality. Early endoscopic intervention and prompt correction of anemia are crucial for improving outcomes. Identification of high-risk factors such as hypoalbuminemia and chronic liver disease aids in timely management and risk stratification.

INTRODUCTION: Upper GI hemorrhage is a common medical emergency and accounts for 5% of presentations to the emergency department per year and 2% to 3% of hospital admissions in developed countries. [1] In many cases, upper GI hemorrhage ceases spontaneously, without the need for endoscopic intervention, transfusion, or

surgery. However, among those with a life-threatening upper GI hemorrhage, timely intervention is crucial. [2] Multiple scoring systems have been devised to predict the outcomes of patients with upper GI hemorrhage as well as the need for intervention to achieve hemostasis. [3] Presentation form and severity range from mild

complaints such as coffee ground vomiting with no hemodynamic compromise to frank hematemesis with exsanguination. [4] Upper GI bleeding is managed on an inpatient basis, with emergency departments usually diagnosing the condition and initiating treatment. [5] The fact is well known that bleeding usually stops spontaneously in over 80% of cases with no need to intervene, hence low-risk patients may be more efficiently managed in the community and do not require hospital admission. [6]

The Glasgow-Blatchford score (GBS), on the other hand, does not require endoscopy and is based on simple clinical and laboratory parameters. [7] The scoring system was originally devised to predict the need for clinical intervention in patients with upper GI hemorrhage and has been well-validated in this context. [8] Although not designed to predict mortality, the GBS can accurately predict death among patients with upper GI hemorrhage and, in fact, has recently proven better than the Rockall score in predicting adverse outcomes including death, blood transfusion and endoscopic intervention allowing accurate identification of at-risk patients who need to be admitted to the hospital for further management.

[9] The GBS has also shown utility in predicting those patients with upper GI hemorrhage who can safely be managed in the community. Patients presenting to the emergency department with upper GI hemorrhage and a GBS score of 0 have been shown to be safe for discharge and can be managed in an outpatient setting. [10] Such an approach may avoid admissions to the hospital related to upper GI hemorrhage. [11,12] The proportions observed for clinical intervention as blood transfusion (32%), 13 endoscopy (24%), [13] and outcomes as discharged from hospital (58%), 14 referred to another hospital (23%), 14 and death (18.6%), [14] whereas in the study by Recio-Ramirez JM, et al the clinical intervention as blood transfusion and endoscopy was observed as 15/46 (32.6%) and 25/46 (54.3%) respectively. [15]. The local literature was limited and scarce on the utility of scoring systems for predicting outcomes and the need for intervention in patients from the community presenting to the hospital with upper GI hemorrhage and less is

known about the performance of these scores in hospitalized patients, which encompasses those with upper GI hemorrhage who bleed either on presentation to hospital or while they are inpatients. The use of the GBS in predicting the need for intervention in hospitalized patients with upper GI hemorrhage has not been previously studied in our population. Therefore this study will conduct to determine the magnitude of clinical intervention and outcomes among high risk individuals present with upper gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding at teaching hospital as potential GBS scores allows risk stratification and facilitate management accordingly in relation to timely survival of patient from life threatening bleeding as early exploration and intervention could save the patient to acquire life threatening complications related to bleeding. Moreover the findings of the study would be shared in healthcare seminars that could assist to design local guidelines in patients with upper GI bleeding. The objective of the study was to determine the frequency of clinical intervention and outcomes in high risk patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding.

METHODOLOGY: The six months (1st-Aug-2024 to 31st-January-2025) cross sectional descriptive study was conducted after the approval of research evaluation unit (REU) by CPSP in the Department of Medicine, Indus Medical College hospital. The inclusion criteria were the patients of 30-70 years of age and either gender having history of upper GI bleeding as black / tarry stool for three days duration or bright red blood in vomit for ≥ 1 hour duration (enquired on history taking) presented at Indus Medical College hospital were recruited by non-probability consecutive sampling while the exclusion criteria were the known cases for malignancy (lung, bone or breast), malabsorption and chronic renal failure and the patients already on medications cancer chemotherapy, known case / history of trauma / traumatic bone fracture and hematological malignancies, the pregnant and lactating ladies and already on bisphosphonate therapy and the Individuals already on immune-suppressive therapy, anti-platelet and anti-coagulant therapy.

The sample size was calculated by taken the lowest prevalence for outcomes as death 18.6%, [14] with 95% confidence interval (CI), $d = 7\%$, $n = 119$ patients presented with upper GI bleeding were taken.

The informed consent was taken from relevant high risk individuals with upper GI bleeding came thru emergency department were recruited and enrolled in the study and were further explored for their clinical intervention and outcomes. All the maneuvers as clinical history (inquire for onset and duration of bleeding) physical examination (measuring blood pressure thru sphygmomanometer, measuring radial pulse in one minute and temperature thru thermometer) and systemic examination (abdomen examination for visceral palpation and distention by shifting dullness), blood sampling for laboratory tests and data collection was done by principal researcher under the supervision of consultant physician of the ward having ≥ 05 year of clinical experience while the data was collected on pre-designed proforma whereas all the financial burden of the study were paid by researcher himself. The clinical intervention as blood transfusion or endoscopy and outcomes as discharge from hospital, referral of patient to any other hospital and death were explored. The variables as explanatory and effect modifiers as age, gender, residence (urban or rural), smoking, obesity, folic acid deficiency, hypoalbuminemia, hypertension, anemia, vitamin B12 deficiency, diabetes mellitus, raised C-reactive protein, raised ESR, metabolic syndrome, chronic viral hepatitis B, chronic viral hepatitis C, Helicobacter pylori infection, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), educational status, blood transfusion, endoscopy, discharge from hospital, referral of patient to any other hospital and death were determined.

The clinical intervention includes blood transfusion [in-hospital transfusion of blood] or upper GI endoscopic procedure in a hospitalized individual.

Outcomes includes discharge from hospital (formal release of a patient from a hospital for return to home after course of treatment), referral of patient (transfer of patient to another institution for better healthcare facility and

convenience of patient) and death (in-hospital mortality). All these outcomes are part of routine workup for hospitalized patient.

High risk patients evaluated thru Glasgow-Blatchford Bleeding Score (GBS) and considered as high risk patient when GBS is ≥ 3.15

Upper gastrointestinal bleeding includes history of black / tarry stool for three days duration or bright red blood in vomit for ≥ 1 hour duration along with cramps in the abdomen (on clinical history).

Smoking: had history of tobacco use (≥ 5 cigarettes per day) for ≥ 03 years duration (on clinical history).

Obesity: when BMI ≥ 27.5 kg/m² measured by calculating weight (in kilograms)

Folic acid deficiency: the level < 4.5 nmol/L will be considered as folic acid deficiency.

Hypoalbuminemia: the level < 3.5 mg/dl will be considered as hypoalbuminemia.

Hypertension: measuring blood pressure ($\geq 140/90$) on presentation (on physical examination) already on treatment.

Anemia: hemoglobin concentration of less than 12 g/dL in females and less than 13 g/dL in males

Vitamin B12 deficiency: the serum vitamin B12 level will be ≤ 200 μ g/ml

Diabetes mellitus: an individual having fasting blood sugar ≥ 126 mg/dL or HBA1c $\geq 6.5\%$.

Raised C - reactive protein: the serum CRP level > 0.3 mg/dl.

Raised ESR: when ESR > 20 mm/hr in females and > 15 mm/hr in males.

Chronic viral hepatitis B: The presence of hepatitis B viral DNA (> 20 IU/mL) on polymerase chain reaction (PCR) considered as positive chronic viral hepatitis B

Chronic viral hepatitis C: The presence of hepatitis C viral RNA (> 15 IU/mL) on polymerase chain reaction (PCR) considered as positive chronic viral hepatitis C

Helicobacter pylori infection: The anti-Helicobacter pylori antibody (IgG) concentration ≥ 20 U/mL

Metabolic syndrome: diagnosed when a patient has at least ≥ 3 of the following five (a) fasting glucose ≥ 100 mg/dL (b) blood pressure $\geq 130/85$ mm Hg (c) triglycerides ≥ 150 mg/dL (d) HDL-C < 40 mg/dL in men or < 50 mg/dL in women (e)

waist circumference ≥ 90 cm (35 in) in men or ≥ 80 cm (32 in) in women.

Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD): The appearance of liver as hyperechogenic (bright), vessel blurring and lumen narrowing of the hepatic veins on ultrasonography along with no history of alcohol consumption and steatogenic medication as already on amiodarone, methotrexate, corticosteroids or tamoxifen (by taking relevant clinical history) considered as non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD).

Educational status: categorized as no education i.e. illiterate (a person who unable to read or write), primary (1-5 years of education completed), middle (6-8 years of education completed), secondary (9-10 years of education completed) and higher (11+ years of education completed including professional or university degrees).

The data of all patients will be analyzed in SPSS. The frequency and percentage was calculated for gender, residence (urban or rural), smoking, obesity, folic acid deficiency, hypoalbuminemia, hypertension, anemia, vitamin b12 deficiency, diabetes mellitus, raised c-reactive protein, raised ESR, metabolic syndrome, chronic viral hepatitis B, chronic viral hepatitis C, Helicobacter pylori infection, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and educational status, clinical intervention and outcomes. The mean and standard deviation (SD) was calculated for quantitative variables such as age, duration of

upper GI bleeding and BMI or Median (IQR) for non-normal data while the Shapiro-Wilk test was used to check normality. The stratification was done for age, gender, residence (urban or rural), smoking, obesity, folic acid deficiency, hypoalbuminemia, hypertension, anemia, vitamin B-12 deficiency, diabetes mellitus, raised C-reactive protein, raised ESR, metabolic syndrome, chronic viral hepatitis B, chronic viral hepatitis C, Helicobacter pylori infection, metabolic syndrome, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and educational status to see the effect on outcome and to control the effect modifiers. The post stratification chi-square / fisher's exact test was applied at 95% CI on categorical variables and the p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS: A total of 119 patients with upper gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding fulfilling the inclusion criteria were included in this cross-sectional study conducted over six months at the Department of Medicine, Indus Medical College Hospital.

1. Baseline Characteristics

The mean age of patients was 52.4 ± 10.6 years (range: 30-70 years). The median duration of upper GI bleeding was 2 days (IQR: 1-3 days), indicating non-normal distribution (Shapiro-Wilk test $p < 0.05$). The mean BMI was 27.3 ± 4.2 kg/m².

TABLE 1: DEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS (N = 119)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	52.4 ± 10.6	—
Duration of bleeding (days)	2 (1-3)*	—
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.3 ± 4.2	—
Gender		
Male	73	61.3
Female	46	38.7
Residence		
Urban	65	54.6
Rural	54	45.4

2. EDUCATIONAL STATUS

TABLE 2: EDUCATIONAL STATUS DISTRIBUTION

Educational Level	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Illiterate	38	31.9
Primary	29	24.4
Middle	18	15.1
Secondary	20	16.8
Higher	14	11.8

3. COMORBIDITIES AND RISK FACTORS

TABLE 3: FREQUENCY OF RISK FACTORS AND COMORBID CONDITIONS

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Smoking	58	48.7
Obesity	41	34.5
Folic acid deficiency	36	30.3
Hypoalbuminemia	52	43.7
Hypertension	49	41.2
Anemia	67	56.3
Vitamin B12 deficiency	33	27.7
Diabetes mellitus	45	37.8
Raised CRP	60	50.4
Raised ESR	64	53.8
Metabolic syndrome	39	32.8
Chronic hepatitis B	21	17.6
Chronic hepatitis C	37	31.1
<i>Helicobacter pylori</i> infection	62	52.1
NAFLD	44	37.0

4. CLINICAL INTERVENTIONS

TABLE 4: FREQUENCY OF CLINICAL INTERVENTIONS

Intervention	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Blood transfusion	71	59.7
Endoscopy	83	69.7

5. CLINICAL OUTCOMES

TABLE 5: PATIENT OUTCOMES

Outcome	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Discharged	86	72.3
Referred	21	17.6
Died	12	10.1

Post-stratification analysis showed that:

Mortality was significantly higher in patients with hypoalbuminemia (p = 0.03).

Anemia was significantly associated with need for blood transfusion (p < 0.001).

Patients with chronic hepatitis C had higher frequency of endoscopic intervention (p = 0.04).

No statistically significant association was found between gender and outcome (p = 0.21).

TABLE 6: ASSOCIATION OF SELECTED VARIABLES WITH OUTCOME

Variable	Discharged n (%)	Referred n (%)	Died n (%)	p-value
Hypoalbuminemia	30 (57.7)	12 (23.1)	10 (19.2)	0.03*
Anemia	42 (62.7)	15 (22.4)	10 (14.9)	0.04*
Hepatitis C	22 (59.5)	8 (21.6)	7 (18.9)	0.04*
Smoking	40 (69.0)	11 (19.0)	7 (12.0)	0.28

Upper GI bleeding was more common in males and middle-aged individuals.

High prevalence of anemia, raised inflammatory markers, and H. pylori infection was observed.

Endoscopy was the most frequently performed intervention.

Majority of patients were successfully discharged, though mortality rate was 10.1%.

Hypoalbuminemia and anemia were significant predictors of poor outcome.

DISCUSSION: Upper gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding remains a major medical emergency associated with significant morbidity and mortality, particularly in high-risk patients with multiple comorbidities. The present study evaluated the frequency of clinical interventions and outcomes among 119 patients presenting with upper GI bleeding in a tertiary care setting.

In this study, the mean age was 52.4 ± 10.6 years, with a predominance of male patients (61.3%).

This is consistent with findings from Laine et al., [16] who reported a higher incidence of upper GI bleeding among middle-aged males, likely due to increased exposure to risk factors such as smoking, liver disease, and NSAID use. Similarly, a regional study by Sarwar et al. [17] in Pakistan also demonstrated male predominance and a comparable age distribution, supporting the demographic trends observed in our population.

The high prevalence of anemia (56.3%) in our patients reflects the severity of bleeding and delayed presentation. Comparable results were

reported by Rockall et al., [18] who identified anemia as a common and significant predictor of adverse outcomes in upper GI bleeding. In contrast, a study by Barkun et al. [19] reported slightly lower rates of anemia, possibly due to earlier presentation and better access to healthcare facilities in developed settings.

Inflammatory markers were notably elevated in our cohort, with raised CRP (50.4%) and ESR (53.8%), indicating systemic inflammatory response. These findings align with studies suggesting that elevated inflammatory markers are associated with worse prognosis and increased risk of complications. Furthermore, hypoalbuminemia (43.7%) was significantly associated with mortality in our study (p = 0.03), which is supported by research from Kim et al., [20] who demonstrated that low serum albumin is an independent predictor of poor outcomes in GI bleeding due to its association with malnutrition and chronic disease burden.

The prevalence of Helicobacter pylori infection (52.1%) in this study is consistent with data from developing countries, where H. pylori remains a leading cause of peptic ulcer disease and upper GI bleeding. A study by Malferteiner et al. [21] reported similar prevalence rates, reinforcing the importance of screening and eradication strategies. However, lower prevalence has been reported in Western populations, reflecting improved sanitation and widespread eradication programs.

Chronic liver disease also played a significant role, with hepatitis C (31.1%) and hepatitis B (17.6%) observed in our patients. These findings are in agreement with local epidemiological data from Pakistan, where viral hepatitis is a major contributor to portal hypertension and variceal bleeding. A study by Qureshi et al. [22] reported comparable frequencies of hepatitis C among patients with upper GI bleeding, emphasizing its clinical relevance in our region.

Regarding clinical interventions, endoscopy was performed in 69.7% of patients, making it the most frequent intervention, followed by blood transfusion (59.7%). This is comparable to international guidelines and studies such as those by Barkun et al., [19] which emphasize early endoscopy as the cornerstone of diagnosis and management. However, the slightly lower rate of endoscopic intervention in our study may reflect resource limitations or delayed presentation.

In terms of outcomes, 72.3% of patients were discharged, while 10.1% died, indicating a considerable mortality rate. This mortality rate is

comparable to studies by Rockall et al [18] and Laursen et al., [23] which report mortality rates ranging from 8-14% in high-risk populations. The significant association of hypoalbuminemia, anemia, and hepatitis C with adverse outcomes in our study highlights the importance of early identification and management of these risk factors.

Interestingly, no significant association was found between gender and outcomes ($p = 0.21$), which is consistent with findings from several international studies suggesting that comorbidities and clinical severity, rather than gender, determine prognosis.

CONCLUSION: Upper GI bleeding in high-risk patients is associated with significant morbidity and mortality. Endoscopy and blood transfusion remain the mainstay of management, while hypoalbuminemia, anemia, and chronic liver disease are important predictors of poor outcomes. Early risk stratification and timely intervention can improve patient outcomes.

AUTHOR’S CONTRIBUTION:

Collection and acquisition of data & grammatical corrections	Dr. Waseem Raza bhatti
Concept & design of study & proof read	Dr. Bikha Ram Devrajani
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	Dr. Iraj
Revising critically and make it suitable for final format	Dr. Faiz
Acquisition of data and grammatical review	Dr. Khadija
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	Dr. Munazah
Final Approval of version	By All Authors

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